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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

HAVE UZBEK, TURKISH AND ENGLISH IDIOMS IN COMMON?

¹ Akramova Fotimakhon Jahongir qizi

² Khazratkulova Ezoza Ismatovna

¹ Student, Chirchik State Pedagogical University, fotimajahangirovna@gmail.com

² Scientific adviser, Chirchiq State Pedagogical University,
khazratkulovae@gmail.com

Annotation: *Certain idioms in different languages sometimes share common background and related historical stories. In fact, learning and understanding foreign languages are much easier by comparing and analyzing language features. The article focuses on some similar idioms in three languages: Uzbek, Turkish and English. Several similar alternatives were analyzed in these languages. Explanations and definitions of certain words will be given below.*

Keywords: phrase, idiom, folk, international language, language family.

Аннотация: *Некоторые идиомы на разных языках иногда имеют общий фон и связанные исторические истории. На самом деле изучать и понимать иностранные языки намного проще, если сравнивать и анализировать языковые особенности. В статье рассматриваются некоторые похожие фразеологизмы в трех языках: узбекском, турецком и английском. В этих языках было проанализировано несколько подобных альтернатив. Пояснения и определения некоторых слов будут даны ниже.*

Ключевые слова: словосочетание, идиома, народный язык, международный язык, языковая семья.

Annotatsiya: *Turli tillardagi ba'zi idiomalar ba'zan umumiy ma'lumot va tegishli tarixiy voqealarni o'rtoqlashadi. Aslida, til xususiyatlarini solishtirish va tahlil qilish orqali chet tillarini o'rganish va tushunish ancha osonlashadi. Maqolada asosiy e'tibor uchta tilda: o'zbek, turk va ingliz tillaridagi o'xshash idiomalarga qaratilgan. Ushbu tillarda bir nechta shunga o'xshash alternativalar tahlil qilindi. Quyida ba'zi so'zlarning tushuntirishlari va ta'riflari keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: iboralar, so'z birikmalari, mahalliy til, xalqaro tillar, til oilalari

Introduction

Every language has its own history and origin. Sometimes culture also influences language development. Related cultures' language features have a lot in common. Language development is viewed as dynamic process, therefore gradually we can face new words and expressions. Being able to speak a particular language fluently is an art, but a person who can also use idioms in it is a real artist. Understanding the meaning of idioms and being able to use them in the right place is not a problem if the language being spoken is our native language. But what if we are speaking another language? Yes, there might be some problems but after reading this article, you can easily handle them. According to the researches of linguists, the

origin of Uzbek and Turkish languages goes back to the same language family. As English is an international language every learner compares some features of his first language with the target one.

Method

The following methods were used in the article: dictionary definitions, and **comparative method** in order to make the general understanding of language similarities and differences of Uzbek, Turkish and English languages. One of the most important methods used in the article is **semantic analysis**. *In linguistics, semantic analysis is the process of relating syntactic structures, from the levels of phrases, clauses, sentences and paragraphs to the level of the writing as a whole, to their language independent meanings. The idioms and figurative speech, being cultural, are often also converted into relatively invariant meanings in semantic analysis. [Goddard, Cliff (2013). Semantic Analysis: An Introduction (2nd ed.). New York: Oxford University Press.p.1].*

Semantic analysis can begin with the relationship between individual words. This requires an understanding of lexical hierarchy, including hyponymy and hypernymy, meronymy, polysemy, synonyms, antonyms, and homonyms. [Manning, Christopher; Scheutze, Hinrich (1999). Foundations of Statistical Natural Language Processing. Cambridge: MIT Press.p.110.]

Discussion

What is the idiom actually? An idiom is the combination of words which a person cannot get the full meaning by translating every word separately. For example, when the phrase “kill two birds with one stone” is used people who have a proficiency of English know that this idiom doesn’t refer to any kind of hurting birds or throwing stones to them. It is time to start the journey.

1. **Uzbek language:** “*Bir o’q bilan ikki quyovni urmoq*”

Turkish language: “*Bir taşla iki kuşvurmak*”

English language: “*Killing two birds with one stone*”

Meaning: Doing two or more tasks in one single action. For example, “While driving, I like listening to audio books. In that way, I can kill two birds with one stone; I go to my destination whilst I learn a lot from the book.”

2.

Uzbek language: “*Ko’z tegmasin*”

Turkish language: “*Nazar değmesin*”

English language: “*Don’t let the evil eye touch you*”

Meaning: “evil eye” usually refers to the misfortune and bad luck, and it equals with “nazar” or “ko’z”. For instance, “You got a promotion less than a week after you were hired and you’re such a handsome guy. *Don’t let the evil eye touch you!*”

3.

Uzbek language: “Peshonasiga yozilgan”

Turkish language: “Alın yazısı”

English language: “is written in the stars”

Meaning: destiny, which means the thing happening in your life have been already decided by God. For example: “You and your girlfriend Anna couldn’t be together, I think it is *written in the stars*”.

4.

Uzbek language: “Xamirdan qil sug’urganday oson”

Turkish language: “Tereyağından kıl çeker gibi”

English language: “like a walk in the park”, “as easy as taking candy from a baby” or “shooting fish in a barrel”.

Meaning: something is as easy to do as pulling a hair out of butter or dough. Pulling a hair out of butter and dough is not a big deal. Example of using the idiom: “The exam questions were *like a walk in the park*. I passed the exam with flying colours”.

5.

Uzbek language: “Tomi ketmoq”

Turkish language: “Keçileri kaçırmak”

English language: “to go bananas”, “to be barking mad”, “to lose the plot”, “to go stir crazy”.

Meaning: losing one’s mind, getting mad, going crazy. According to Turkish stories, so many years ago there was a shepherd who brings the herd of goats to the the same place everyday where goats could eat grass. But one day, a shepherd fell asleep under the shadow of a tree, when he opened his eyes after a while, there were no goats around. He starts to run to the village, saying “Keçileri kaçırdım, keçileri kaçırdım” (I lost the goats, I lost the goats). When all people arrived at the spot where he claimed to have lost the goats, the all goats were there and they hadn’t been lost, but went to the river to drink some water and came back. Village folk believed that the shepherd got mad. Since then the idiom “Keçileri kaçırmak” is used to express someone has gone mad.

Result

Learning idioms, remembering and understanding them fully will help language learners to improve their language skills. Especially comparative learning method is one of the most common and useful ways of learning. After doing some

research on comparative languages, I started speaking fluently in both English and Turkish.

Conclusion

Hence, learning new languages is not easy. However, if you learn it by comparing to other languages that you know well, the process goes much easier. Uzbek and Turkish are a lot in common both in culture and language. Studying English idioms by using alternatives is helpful for both nations.

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